

Evaluation and selection of AC transmission lay-outs for large offshore wind farms.

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Abstract

This paper studies different energy transmission solutions for AC offshore wind farms. This transmission of energy is based on AC submarine cables that present a strong capacitive behavior. Therefore, an analysis is necessary to determine transmission characteristics such as, the number of submarine cables, voltage or rated power.

For that purpose, three different transmission configurations will be considered: unique HVAC, various HVAC and MVAC, combined with three submarine cables of different characteristics.

By using a design procedure, it is shown that based on the electric characteristics provided by the manufacturer of the submarine cable, it is possible to determine the most efficient energy transmission solution, from the perspective of the submarine cable. Different variables will be taken into account, including transmission current, active power losses, the cost of the transmitted energy and the reactive power compensation required. In addition, the consequences of the selected transmission solution to other more general aspects of the wind farm such as, necessity of the offshore platform or local inter-turbine network are also discussed.

I. Introduction

There are several options to transfer the generated energy in a offshore wind farm to the distribution grid. These options range from the HVDC (High Voltage Direct Current) connection to various MVAC (Medium Voltage Altern Current) connections. Also, within these options there are different variants [1]. Considering the AC connections, the different lay-outs are divided into two families: HVAC (High Voltage AC transmission) connection and MVAC connection. The difference between these two AC families is the offshore platform. HVAC connection needs an offshore substation to accommodate the step up transformer. On the contrary, MVAC connection avoids elements and power transformer at sea [2].

Within these two AC families, there are different design options. These options are determined by the number of submarine cables to connect the offshore wind farm with the grid and the voltage level of

connection. For instance, in Krieger's Flak wind farm a transmission system with multiple HVAC connections is planned [3].

Unique MVAC transmission system is only used in very small wind farms, which means that large offshore wind farms use multiple MVAC transmission systems. In this last configuration, the wind farm is divided into different clusters and connected directly to the grid. The connection is made at the same voltage level of the local wind farm grid 24-26kV, therefore, the transmission system does not need an offshore platform. The only transformers required are located at the base of the wind turbine tower, to adapt the generator's voltage [4].

The energy transmission between the wind farm and the grid is made with submarine cables. These cables present a high shunt capacitance, hence, submarine cables generate a large amount of reactive power. This reactive power causes one of the biggest problems of the AC offshore wind farms transmission system [5], [6], the rated current of the cable is thermally limited. Thus, as the length of the cable increases, their shunt capacitance and the charging currents increase as well, leading to a reduction in the active current carrying capability of the cable.

One way to compensate or minimize as much as possible such effects, is to compensate the reactive power. Therefore, reactive power compensation is a variable to be taken into account when selecting the transmission lay-out, since an appropriate compensation can improve the characteristics of the submarine cables [7].

The compensation of this reactive power can be made at one end (onshore) or in both ends (onshore and offshore). Even so, to optimize the use of the cable or to increase the useful distance of the cable, a compensation at both ends is required [8].

Therefore, for a specific AC offshore wind farm, depending on these two variables: rated power and location, it is possible to define the amount and the location of the reactive power compensation, the number of cables to use in the transmission system and their voltage level. In conclusion, the electrical lay-out.

Several analyses about the energy production cost based on the produced energy and the investment cost are carried out in [1], [9]. These studies are focused on the comparison between AC transmission options and DC transmission options. More specifically, the analysis in [9] is based on very high rated powers 400-1000MW.

These studies do not consider in detail the reactive power compensation or different AC transmission options at different rated powers and voltages. Therefore, this paper tries to complete these analyses.

II. Offshore AC wind farm lay-outs

The different connection lay-outs present different combinations in these three aspects: number of cables, transmission voltage and transmitted power by each cable. Therefore, AC power transmission configurations for large offshore wind farms, can be classified into three groups: HVAC, multiple HVAC and multiple MVAC.

HVAC High voltage AC transmission

HVAC lay-out is commonly used by large offshore wind farms such as: Barrow - 90MW, Nysted - 158MW or Horns Rev - 160MW. The general electrical layout of the HVAC offshore wind farm, depicted in Fig. 1, consist of the wind farm, the offshore substation (step-up transformer), the submarine cable, the interface between the wind farm and the point of common coupling (substation) and the grid.

Fig. 1: General layout of HVAC offshore wind farm.

The inter-turbine network is typically medium voltage 20-36kV (Horns Rev 24kV, Barrow 33kV o Nysted 34kV). The inter-turbine network extends from each wind turbine to the collecting point, This network is medium voltage, due to the fact that it may have a length of kilometers [10] In the collecting point the voltage is increased to the transmission system required level (Barrow 132kV, Nysted 132kV, Horns Rev 150kV) and then transfers the energy to the interface with the network (substation), to integrate the energy into the transmission network.

MVAC Medium voltage AC transmission

This electrical configuration, is based on dividing the wind farm into smaller groups or clusters and directly connecting each clusters to the shore. The general layout of this configuration is shown in Fig. 2. In MVAC, the transmission voltage is the same as the inter-turbine network, i.e. medium voltage between 20 and 36kV. Hence, this electrical configuration avoids the offshore platform and its cost. This type of electric configuration is used by small wind farms located near to the shore. For example: Middelgrunden (30kV-40MW) at 3Km to shore, Scroby Sands (33kV-60MW) located 2.3Km seaward o North Hoyle (33kV -60MW) at 7-8Km offshore.

Fig. 2: General layout of MVAC offshore wind farm.

The main problem of the medium voltage transmission is the conduction losses in the submarine cables. To transfer the same energy, at medium voltage (MV) compared with high voltage (HV), the system needs more current and the submarine cable losses are related to the magnitude of the current. Another problem is that the MVAC lay-out needs more kilometers of subsea cable. Therefore, this layout must find a compromise between saving money by avoiding an offshore platform and the cost of subsea cables.

Using an energy transmission at medium voltage eliminates the offshore platform, but increases the number of installed subsea cables and it is also possible to increase the conduction losses.

Multiple HVAC

This electrical configuration is a combination of the previous two configurations. The wind farm is divided into smaller clusters but these clusters are not connected directly to shore. In this case, at each cluster there exists a collecting point. At the collecting point, the voltage is increased to the transmission system required level. The general layout of this configuration is illustrated in Fig. 3. Offshore wind farms with multiple HVAC transmission systems have large rated power, for example Kriegers Flak (640MW) or Robin Rigg (East/west – 180MW). These wind farms are under construction.

Fig. 3: General layout of offshore wind farm with multiple HVAC connections.

In this electrical configuration, the transmission voltage can be different to the inter-turbine network voltage. In the same way, transmitted power through a line depends on the number of clusters. Thus, multiple and different combinations are possible.

This electrical configuration needs several offshore substations to increase the voltage. Another option is to place several transformers in the same platform, but in both cases the cost is increased.

III. Procedure to calculate the energy transmission cost

In this paper, the appropriate selection of the transmission layout is based on a transmission cost analysis. The block diagram of the procedure to calculate the transmission cost, is depicted in Fig. 4.

Firstly, the reactive power compensation of the transmission system is defined (location and quantity). At the same time, the produced energy at the offshore wind farm is calculated, as a function of the rated power and the average wind speed. Next, the transmission lay-out is defined: N° of clusters, transmission voltage level and the cable length.

Then, the active power losses of the transmission system are calculated, to obtain the transmitted energy. Finally, the transmission cost is defined as the investment cost (estimated operating and maintenance, O&M cost included) of the transmission system divided with the transmitted power. Therefore, energy transmission cost in €/kWh is obtained.

Fig. 4: Block diagram of the layout selection procedure.

IV. Submarine cable model

This evaluation is focused on the selection of the AC transmission lay-out for offshore wind farms.

The dynamic behavior of the transmission system has not been taken into account. The submarine cable has been modeled at steady-state operation. The frequency response of the cable model for higher frequencies than the fundamental is not important for this analysis.

The submarine cables at each differential length they also have a resistive, inductive and capacitive component. The submarine cables have lumped parameters. Generally manufactures provide the parameters as a function of the length. In this paper 3 different cables have been studied, as shown in Table I.

Table I: Submarine cable characteristics.

Cable	Vn (kV)	In(A)	Rc (Ω /Km)	L (mH/Km)	C (μ F/Km)
A	36/66	911	0.0221	0.294	0.331
B	87/150	1088	0.0151	0.352	0.233
C	220	1055	0.048	0.37	0.18

To carry out a model simplification, the parameters are concentrated in an equivalent simplified model. For submarine cables which have a big capacitive component, models that take this factor into account are usually used. For example, models based on “ π ” circuits or RLC circuits [11]. In this paper, submarine cables are modeled by “ π ” equivalent circuits. Some authors [12], [13], have also adopted simplified “ π ” models for this analysis.

To know the value of the current and energy along the submarine cable, the cable is divided into 4 sections and each section is modeled as a “ π ” circuit. The model that has been used for this analysis is shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5:Used submarine cable model.

where: Long: cable length, R_c : Resistance of the cable section, L : Inductance of the cable section, C : Capacitance of the cable section.

In order to the wind farm, there is modeled as a controlled P,Q node.

V. Reactive power compensation

The submarine cables present a high shunt capacitance, this effect causes the capacitive charging and discharging currents in the cable which generates reactive power. The rated current of the cable is thermally limited. Thus, as the length of the cables increase, their shunt capacitance and the charging currents increase as well. As a consequence, the load carrying capability of the cable is reduced.

In order to use the submarine cable without a length limit and reduce conduction losses, the ideal solution is a distributed compensation of the reactive power along the length of the submarine cable. This option is not possible in submarine cables. The second option is to compensate the reactive power at both ends [5].

Minimizing as possible the reactive current through the cable, the conduction losses are reduced and the load carrying capability increases.

There are many options to compensate the energy at both ends, but this paper does not take into account how the reactive power is compensated. In this evaluation two aspects of the reactive power compensation are considered: amount and location. Therefore, two cases are compared.

In the first case, the wind farm produced energy with a unity power factor and the reactive power produced on the submarine cable, is compensated onshore.

In the second case, the objective of the compensation is to minimize the reactive current through the cable. Hence, the best compensation supplies the same current at both ends. The best option, compensates half of the reactive power produced in the cable offshore and the other half onshore. The reactive power produced in the submarine cable varies with the load, therefore, this reactive power compensation must be dynamic.

Fig. 6, shows the current along the cable for different lengths, with onshore compensation and compensation at both ends. In the case of the onshore compensation, for different cable lengths, circulates the same current at the same length. On the contrary, with a compensation of 50% of the reactive power at each ends, the minimum current appear in the middle of the cable and the maximum currents in both ends. Finally, it must be emphasized that the maximum current with a compensation at both ends is significantly minor than the maximum current with onshore compensation.

Fig. 6: Module of the current through the submarine cable vs cable length. With compensation at both ends (red) and onshore compensation (blue). a) 5x30MW-36kV configuration. b) 150MW-150kV

The compensation of the reactive power at both ends minimizes the current through the cable for all the cables and all the electrical configurations. The reactive power compensation is an important variable to select a lay-out of the offshore wind farm: This is because with an inadequate compensation the cable can be unusable or have a increase in conduction losses. In Fig. 6 (b) at 200Km with onshore compensation the cable it becomes unusable, but with compensation at both ends is usable. Therefore, it is important to firstly determine the reactive power compensation.

VI. Active power losses for different lay-outs

Considered lay-outs

The rated power of the considered wind farm is 150 MW. However, in different electric configurations the wind farm can be divided into clusters. This evaluation has considered 2x75MW, 3x50MW and 5x30MW.

The voltage level is another important characteristic of the transmission system. Hence, in this evaluation several transmission voltages from medium voltage (36kV) to high voltages (66kV,87kV,150kV and 220kV) are taken into account. Therefore, depending on the N° of clusters and transmission voltage an suitable cable is used, as shown in Table II.

Table II: Used cable for each electric configuration.

Cable	Electric configurations
A	2x750MW-66kV / 2x750MW-66kV / 3x50MW-66kV / 3x50MW-36kV / 5x30MW-36kV
B	150MW-150kV / 2x750MW-87kV
C	150MW-220kV

Referring to the reactive power compensation, in this evaluation a compensation at both ends is considered for all the layouts.

Conduction losses

The active power losses in the transmission system, are a very representative variable for designing the transmission layout. This is due to the fact that, with the investment needed to build the layout, the active power losses difference between two layouts, impose the income difference.

In this evaluation, five different configurations are considered, for a 150 MW wind farm with a compensation of the 50% of the reactive power at each ends.

The reason for focusing the analysis on to a compensation in both ends of the submarine cables, is because that compensation considerably reduces the active power losses at any transmitted power level, for all the layouts, as can be derived from Fig. 7.

Fig. 7: Active power losses for 50km cable length, with compensation at both ends (red) and onshore compensation (blue) a) 150MW-150kV, 2x75MW-87kV, 3x50MW-66kV y 5x30MW-36kV configurations b) 150MW-220kV

$$P_{loss} = \text{Re}(\vec{V}_p \cdot \vec{I}_p) - \text{Re}(\vec{V}_o \cdot \vec{I}_o) \quad (1)$$

The average active power losses of the transmission system are on function of 4 variables: wind farms rated power, distance to shore, average wind speed and reactive power compensation.

The wind speed can be treated as a continuous random variable. The probability that a wind speed shall occur can be described with a Rayleigh distribution [1], [9], equation (2). The Rayleigh distribution for different average wind speed is shown in figure Fig. 8 (a).

$$R(v_{wind}) = \frac{k}{c} \cdot \left(\frac{v_s}{c}\right)^{k-1} \cdot e^{-\left(\frac{v_s}{c}\right)^k} \quad (2)$$

Where: $R(v_{wind})$ is probability density, v_{wind} is wind speed (m/s), k is shape parameter (=2) and c is scale parameter.

On the other hand, in equation (3), the produced active power on the wind farm on function of the wind speed and turbine characteristics is calculated (Fig. 8(b)).

$$P_t(v) = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \rho \cdot \pi \cdot R^2 \cdot V_{wind}^3 \cdot Cp \quad (3)$$

Where: $P_t(v)$ =Generated power in function of the wind speed, ρ = air density, R =Wind turbine radio, V_{wind} =Wind speed, Cp = Aerodynamic efficiency.

Fig. 8: a) Rayleigh distribution for different average wind speeds b) Generated power on wind farm on function of the wind speed.

Hence, it is possible to obtain the produced average power, equation (4). This evaluation is focused in the transmission system, therefore losses in generators and losses in inter-turbine network have not been taken into account. These losses, are the same for all the layouts and only affect to the amount of the active power produced.

$$P_{avg} = \int_{V_{on}}^{V_{cut}} P(v) \cdot R(v) \cdot dv \quad (4)$$

Where: P_{avg} =Average input power, V_{cut} = cut out wind speed (30m/s), V_{on} = cut in wind speed (3,5m/s), $P(v)$ =Input power in function of the wind speed, $R(v)$ =probability distribution (Rayleigh).

Linking the active power losses on function of the transmitted power level (Fig. 7) with produced active power on function of the wind speed (equation (3)). It is possible to obtain the active power losses on function of the wind speed. Finally, with the wind speed distribution probability the average active power losses can be calculated:

$$P_{loss,avg} = \int_{V_{on}}^{V_{cut}} P_{loss}(v) \cdot R(v) \cdot dv \quad (5)$$

Where: $P_{loss,avg}$ =Average active power losses, V_{cut} = cut out wind speed (30m/s), V_{on} = cut in wind speed (3,5m/s), $P(v)$ =Input power in function of the wind speed, $R(v)$ =probability distribution (Rayleigh).

VII. Energy transmission cost for different lay-outs

With the average losses of the transmission system, depending on the distance for different configurations, it is possible to calculate the difference in MWh of transmitted power throughout the cables life time.

Therefore, with the investment cost and operating and maintenance cost it is possible to obtain the energy transmission cost for different layouts.

Transmitted energy

The submarine cables have a failure rate. This failure rate is considered 0,1/year/100Km [14]. In the same way, the main time to repair (MTTR) is considered 3 months. The availability of the submarine cables is calculated in equation (6).

In cases with multiple connections to onshore (wind farm divided into clusters) redundant connections between clusters are considered. However when one cable fails, transmission at rated power is impossible. Also, with the increase of the installed cables the error provability increases too. So, the same availability of the cables is considered at the same distance to onshore as a simplification.

$$A_{cable} = \frac{t_{life} - n \cdot \frac{long}{100} \cdot N \cdot t_{repair}}{t_{life}} \quad (6)$$

Where: A_{cable} = Cable availability, t_{life} = Life time (month), n = Failure rate (failure/100Km/year), $long$ = submarine cable length, N = Life time (year), t_{repair} = MTTR (month).

For electrical configurations with offshore platform, it is considered the availability of the step-up transformer. The failure rate is considered 0,03/year with 6 month of MTTR [15]. The availability of the transformer is described below:

$$A_{rafo} = \frac{t_{life} - n \cdot N \cdot t_{repair}}{t_{life}} \quad (7)$$

Where: A_{rafo} = Cable availability, t_{life} = Life time (month), n = Failure rate (failure/100Km/year), $long$ = submarine cable length, N = Life time (year), t_{repair} = MTTR (month).

The transmitted energy is calculated with equation (8). The results are calculated for 8 m/s average wind speed and 20 years life time.

$$E_{trans} = (P_{avg} - P_{loss,avg}) \cdot t \cdot A \quad (8)$$

Where: E_{trans} = Transmitted energy, P_{avg} = Average generated power, $P_{loss,avg}$ = Average active power losses, t = Life time (h), A = Availability.

Cost of the connection infrastructure

With regards the cost of the connection infrastructure, the cost of the following elements were considered in the evaluation: transformer, offshore platform (if required), submarine cables, installation of submarine cables and reactive power compensators.

- Cost of the offshore platform [2].

$$C_{plataform} = 2.14 + 0.0747 \cdot P_{rated} \quad (9)$$

$C_{plataform}$ = Cost of the offshore platform (M€), P_{rated} = Rated power of the wind farm (MW)

- Cost of the transformer [9]. Cost of the step-up transformer of the offshore platform.

$$C_{transformer} = 0.03327 \cdot P^{0.7513} \quad (10)$$

$C_{transformer}$ = Cost of the transformer (M€), P = Rated power of the transformer (MVA).

- Cost of cable installation, this cost depends on the location of the wind farm and is difficult to estimate accurately. In this evaluation for cases with more than one line needing to connect to onshore it is considered that all the submarine cables are installed together. The cost of the installation is estimated at 0.256 M€/Km [2].
- Cost of the submarine cables (estimation). This cost can have high fluctuations on function of the market.

Table III: Submarine cable cost.

	36kV	66kV	87kV	150kV	220kV
€/km	200.000	300.000	400.000	500.000	600.000

- Cost of the static reactive power compensation [9].

$$C_{comp} = 0.02218 \cdot Q^{0.7513} \quad (11)$$

C_{comp} = Cost of the reactive power compensation (M€), Q = Reactive power to compensate (MVAR).

Cost of operating and maintenance

- Maintenance of the submarine cables. Submarine cable failure rate is considered 0,1/year/100Km and the life time of 20 years. The reparation cost for one XLPE 3-Core 132kV submarine cable is estimated at 3 M£ (3.3 M€). On the other hand, the reparation cost for one XLPE 3-Core 220kV to 400kV is estimated on 4.4 M£ (4.85 M€) [16]. There are a limited number of companies with capability to install an repair submarine cables. Hence the reparation costs are increasing and this costs depends strongly on the market. In this paper, for submarine cables with lower voltages than 132kV (36kV/66k/87kV) the reparation cost it is considered at 3.3 M€ and for submarine cables with higher voltages than 132kV (150kV/220kV) at 4.85 M€.
- Maintenance of the offshore transformer. The step-up transformer on the offshore platform has a 0,3/year failure rate and the life time is considered to be 20 years. So, the failure probability in the life time is 0,6 and the reparation cost is considered 2,5 M£ (2,75 M€) [15].

Cost of the energy transmission in €/kWh

Transmission cost (€/kWh) is calculated using the transmitted energy and the cost of the transmission infrastructure and maintenance.. The invest is paid through offshore wind farm life time. The total invest cost is calculated as follow [9]:

$$C_{invest} = \frac{r \cdot (1+r)^N \cdot N}{((1+r)^N - 1)} \cdot Invest \quad (12)$$

Where: C_{invest} = Total investment cost, r = Interest rate (4%), N = Life time (years), $Invest$ = Investment cost today.

Finally, The energy transmission cost is calculated in equation (13) and the results for different layouts are shown in Fig. 9.

$$C_{trans} = \frac{C_{invest}}{E_{trans}} \quad (13)$$

Where: C_{trans} = Energy transmission cost (€/kWh), C_{invest} = Total investment cost, E_{trans} = Transmitted energy.

Fig. 9: Energy transmission cost for different layouts.

VIII. Conclusion

In agreement with built wind farms, a MVAC transmission system is the best option near to shore. This is because submarine cables are very expensive. With big cable lengths the cables costs do not compensate the money saved in the offshore platform.

With short cable lengths (<20Km) MVAC connections are better than other layouts. Moreover, at 150 MW rated power MVAC configuration can be the best option to 60Km cable length. However in this case the clusters are of (40-50MW) and the submarine cables operates at 70-80% (or more depending the cable length) of their load capability. This can cause an inadmissible voltage drop in the transmission system or other harmful effects.

In this paper only conduction losses in the submarine cables have been considered, armor losses or dielectric losses have also not been taken into account. But this simplification affect to cable parameterization and not to layout selection procedure.

220kV HVAC system is not the best option for any cable length. But the cable used in this evaluation has 3 times higher resistive component than other cables.

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